

Resistance^a of rice varieties to sheath blotch in Kaul, India.

Lesion length (mm)	Group	Variety
10-15	1	IET7662, IET7738, IET7753, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR17494-32-1-1-3-3, RP2151-21-1, RP2151-33-4, RP2151-7752, RP2240-86-84, CN758-1-1-1, UPR80-149.
15-30	2	Jaya, Ratna, HKR101, HAU3800-1, HAU3855-1, RP1832-23-34, RP2151-27-1.
30-45	3	HAU101-88, RP2151-76-1.
45-60	4	HAU47-6045-1, HAU101-60.
>60	5	IET7641, IR19661-23-3-2-2.

^a Resistant = groups 1 and 2, moderately resistant = group 3, susceptible = groups 4 and 5.

ricefields in Haryana. The disease appears as irregular and brownish lesions that enlarge and become sepia-colored. The middle portion of the lesion finally turns whitish and is studded with pycnidia, the characteristic symptom of the disease.

We conducted a roving survey 15-18 Oct 1986, when the rice crop was at the dough to maturity stage. Disease incidence was recorded on both sides of the road every 8 km. Of 52 villages, in Ambala, Jind, Karnal, and Kurukshetra districts, disease was found in 11 villages, more in Kurukshetra than in other districts. No disease was found in

Hisar and Sirsa districts. Disease incidence was higher on rice variety PR107, followed by Jaya, Basmati, and PR106.

Incidence on varieties or genotypes grown under field conditions at Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kaul, was measured during 1986 wet season. Those varieties were categorized into five groupings on the basis of lesion length on the outer leaf sheath. Entries with lesion lengths 1-30 mm were categorized as resistant; 30-45 mm, moderately resistant; and more than 45 mm, susceptible (see table). □

Insect resistance

Registration of brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant germplasm lines in Japan

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Breeding to introduce the BPH resistance gene from indica to japonica rice varieties started in 1968. Since then, we have developed four japonica type lines, each with one of four different resistance genes (*Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, and *bph 4*) (see table).

Norin PL 3, with the *Bph 1* gene, was selected from the cross F₆ 324/ Akitsuho // Tsukushibare. F₆ 324 is the donor parent, with *Bph 1* from Hoyoku/ Mudgo/2/ Kochikaze/3/ IR781-1-94/4/Hoyoku. In 1984, Norin PL 3 was registered as a germplasm line by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF), Japan.

Norin PL 4 inherited *bph 2* from IRI 154-243 through the cross combination of Asominori/ IRI 154-2431 / 2*Asominori. It was registered in 1985.

Norin PL 7 from the cross Tsukushibare *2/ Babawee inherited *bph*

Germplasm lines with BPH resistance.

Line	Resistance gene	Donor parent	Days to heading	Culm length (cm)
Norin PL 3	<i>Bph 1</i>	Mudgo	128	71
Norin PL 4	<i>bph 2</i>	IR1154-243	128	67
Norin PL 7	<i>bph 4</i>	Babawee	127	83
Norin PL 10	<i>Bph 3</i>	Rathu Heenati	131	80
Tsukushibare	—	—	130	73
Asominori	—	—	130	76

4 from Babawee. It was registered in 1987.

Norin PL 10, selected from the cross Tsukushibare/3/Tsukushibare*3/ Rathu Heenati /Tsukushibare, inherited *Bph 3* from Rathu Heenati. It was registered in 1988.

The antibiosis of these lines to BPH is similar to or slightly weaker than that of the donor indica varieties. The lines show inhibitory effect on BPH survival and population increase and different reactions to the biotypes.

Their morphological characteristics are mostly those of japonica varieties, except for a few traits, such as the amylose content of Norin PL 10.

When these lines are crossed with other japonica varieties, the F₁ does not show hybrid sterility, except with Norin PL 7. Partial seed sterility was observed in F₁ plants of Norin PL 7/a Japanese line.

These four lines are being used to breed BPH-resistant varieties in Japan. □

Rice resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* in Bangladesh

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WBPH incidence has increased in recent years, particularly in the irrigated boro (Dec-Mar) crop. We screened BRRI varieties BR1-BR12 and BR14-BR21 and 22 IR varieties, using the standard seedbox test. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Seedlings (20/ 12-cm row) were infested with 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs

from a stock culture, at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was measured (Standard evaluation system for rice 0 to 9 scale) 10 d after infestation, when all TN1 seedlings were killed.

All test varieties except IR64 were susceptible (see table). IR64, which exhibited moderate resistance, is not grown in Bangladesh.

We screened 18 BRRI elite breeding lines, 41 promising exotic varieties, and 23 local germplasm collections using the same procedure. Only BR1711-7-24-2

Reaction of BR and IR varieties to WBPH in Bangladesh. BRRI, Gazipur, 1987.

Variety	Plant damage score ^a	Reaction ^b
BR1	9.0	S
BR2	8.3	S
BR3	7.7	S
BR4	8.3	S
BR5	9.0	S
BR6	9.0	S
BR7	8.3	S
BR8	7.0	S
BR9	7.0	S
BR10	8.3	S
BR11	7.7	S
BR12	7.7	S
BR14	7.7	S
BR15	8.3	S
BR16	7.7	S
BR17	9.0	S
BR18	7.7	S
BR19	9.0	S
BR20	9.0	S
BR21	9.0	S
IR5	8.3	S
IR8	9.0	S
IR20	9.0	S
IR22	9.0	S
IR24	9.0	S
IR26	9.0	S
IR28	7.7	S
IR29	8.3	S
IR30	8.3	S
IR32	8.3	S
IR34	8.3	S
IR36	8.3	S
IR38	8.3	S
IR40	9.0	S
IR42	9.0	S
IR44	7.7	S
IR45	7.0	S
IR46	7.0	S
IR50	7.7	S
IR52	7.0	S
IR56	6.3	MS
IR64	5.0	MR

^aAverage of 3 sets, scored on a scale of 0-9
^bS = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, R = moderately resistant.

and BR2070-15-6, exotic variety Lua Ngu (Vietnam), and local varieties Rajasail 3 and Rajasail 8 (BRRI acc. no. 2436 and 2440) were moderately resistant.

While varieties with moderate resistance may be planted if WBPH incidence is low, the breeding lines identified will require further

improvement and evaluation before they can be released.

Babawee, Hondarwala, Rathu Heenati, and Gangala are resistant to WBPH at IRRI, but susceptible at BRRI. Further studies are needed to determine whether the differential varietal reactions are due to differences in WBPH populations. □

A potential donor for resistance to the gall midge (GM) population of Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated four donors and two derivatives against the GM population of Srikakulam during rainy season 1988. Twenty-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted in 3-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded

in 21 hills at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Only Banglei showed no GM (see table), and could be a donor for resistance to the GM population of Srikakulam District. The other potential donors (Eswarakora, Leaug 152, and Velluthacheera) showed no resistance. The two GM-resistant derivatives, W 1263 (MTU 15/ Eswarakora) and Phalguna (IR8/Siam 29), also did not show resistance reaction to the local GM population.

In view of these reactions of proven donors and derivatives, we strongly suspect the existence of a new GM biotype in the district. □

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. Srikakulam District, A. P., India, 1988.

Variety	Parentage	GM incidence (%)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		Hill	Tiller	Hill	Tiller
Eswarakora	Donor	23.8	2.9	47.6	3.1
W1263	MTUIS/Eswarakora	38.1	5.5	81.0	9.8
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	42.9	7.5	90.5	24.1
Leaug 152	Donor	28.6	4.5	85.7	13.9
Velluthacheera	Donor	9.5	1.0	57.1	6.2
Banglei	Donor	0	0	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	69.0	8.9	100.0	27.2

Screening for resistance to rice gall midge (GM)

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason is a major pest in India. This pest attacks the

rice crop in the plateau region of Bihar, both upland and lowland. Six GM biotypes have been identified (one each in China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and in Andhra Pradesh and Orissa in India). The biotype at Ranchi appears to be different (Table 1).

In 1986 wet season, 60 rice genotypes received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad,